

Supporting information

1. Chemical synthesis

N(Me)₄/F5-3PB-OH. Tris(pentafluorophenyl)borane (1 eq., 200 mg, 0.391 mmol) was dissolved in 1 ml of DCM and tetramethylammonium hydroxide solution (25% w/w, aqueous) (10 eq., 1.4 mL, 3.91 mmol) was added. This two-phase system was stirred vigorously for 10 min, then phases were separated and the aqueous phase was extracted two times with DCM. The DCM fractions were combined, dried over sodium sulphate, and after solvent evaporation 197 mg (0.328 mmol, 84%) of tetramethylammonium hydroxytris(pentafluorophenyl)borate (**N(Me)₄/F5-3PB-OH**) was obtained as white crystals. ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -136.66 (2 F, d, *J*=23 Hz), -164.15 (1 F, br t, *J*=20 Hz), -167.93 (2 F, br t, *J*=19 Hz). ¹¹B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -4.00 (1 B, s). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm 3.06 (12 H, br s), 1.50 (1 H, br s).

Figure S1. FNMR of **N(Me)₄/F5-3PB-OH** in acetonitrile-*d*₃.

Figure S2. BNMR of $N(\text{Me})_4/\text{F5-3PB-OH}$ in acetonitrile- d_3 .

Figure S3. HNMR of $N(\text{Me})_4/\text{F5-3PB-OH}$ in acetonitrile- d_3 .

General procedure for synthesis of R18/counterion pairs

10 mg (0.012 mmol) of Rhodamine B octadecyl ester perchlorate (**R18/CIO₄**) was mixed with 3-10 equivalents of the appropriate counterion salt in DCM and the mixture was sonicated for 5 minutes. Products of ion exchange were purified on preparative TLC plates using DCM/MeOH mixtures as eluent. Results are summarized in the Table S1.

R18/BF₄. ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -151.82 (s) (¹⁰B coupling), -151.87 (s) (¹¹B coupling). ¹¹B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -1.18 (s).

Figure S4. FNMR of **R18/BF₄** in acetonitrile-*d*₃.

Figure S5. BNMR of **R18/BF₄** in acetonitrile-*d*₃.

R18/PF₆. ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -72.93 (d, *J*=706 Hz). ³¹P NMR (162 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -144.65 (sept, *J*=706 Hz).

Figure S6. FNMR of **R18/PF₆** in acetonitrile-*d*₃.

Figure S7. PNMR of **R18/PF₆** in acetonitrile-d₃.

R18/B(CN)₄. ¹¹B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -38.64 (s).

Figure S8. BNMR of **R18/B(CN)₄** in acetonitrile-*d*₃.

R18/B(CF₃)₄. ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -62.91 (q, *J*=26 Hz). ¹¹B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm -19.02 (m, *J*=26 Hz).

Figure S9. FNMR of **R18/B(CF₃)₄** in acetonitrile-*d*₃.

Figure S10. BNMR of **R18/B(CF₃)₄** in acetonitrile-*d*₃.

R18/F5-3PB-OH. ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, acetonitrile- d_3) δ ppm -136.53 (2 F, d, $J=23$ Hz), -163.95 (1 F, br t, $J=19$ Hz), -167.83 (2 F, br t, $J=19$ Hz). ^{11}B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile- d_3) δ ppm -4.02 (1 B, s).

Figure S11. FNMR of **R18/F5-3PB-OH** in acetonitrile- d_3 .

Figure S12. BNMR of **R18/F5-3PB-OH** in acetonitrile- d_3 .

R18/B₂₁H₁₈. ¹¹B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile-*d*₃) δ ppm 4.67 (6 B, d, *J*=170 Hz), 1.83 (6 B, d, *J*=144 Hz), -18.44 (6 B, d, *J*=144 Hz), -20.60 (3 B, s).

Figure S13. BNMR of **R18/B₂₁H₁₈** in acetonitrile-*d*₃.

R18/F5-TPB. ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, acetonitrile- d_3) δ ppm -133.66 (2 F, s), -163.89 (1 F, br t, $J=19$ Hz), -168.26 (2 F, br t, $J=17$ Hz). ^{11}B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile- d_3) δ ppm -16.70 (1 B, s).

Figure S14. FNMR of R18/F5-TPB in acetonitrile- d_3 .

Figure S15. BNMR of R18/F5-TPB in acetonitrile- d_3 .

R18/F6-TPB. ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, acetonitrile- d_3) δ ppm -63.21 (1 F, s). ^{11}B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile- d_3) δ ppm -6.66 (1 B, s).

Figure S16. FNMR of **R18/F6-TPB** in acetonitrile- d_3 .

Figure S17. BNMR of **R18/F6-TPB** in acetonitrile- d_3 .

R18/F12-TPB. ^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, acetonitrile- d_3) δ ppm -71.82 (1 F, s). ^{11}B NMR (128 MHz, acetonitrile- d_3) δ ppm -5.94 (1 B, s).

Figure S18. FNMR of **R18/F12-TPB** in acetonitrile- d_3 .

Figure S19. BNMR of **R18/F12-TPB** in acetonitrile- d_3 .

2. Supplementary figures

Figure S20. Size distribution by volume of the tested PLGA NPs at 50 mM dye loading. Data for three consecutive measurements are shown.

Figure S21. Influence of β-cyclodextrin on the absorption spectra of R18/ClO₄ in water. 2 µM solution of R18/ClO₄ dye in water was treated with various amounts of β-cyclodextrin. The spectra show that β-cyclodextrin helps to dissolve aggregates of R18/ClO₄ dye in water, sufficient concentration being about 1 mM. Dilution due to addition of β-cyclodextrin was less than 10%.

Figure S22. Normalized fluorescence spectra of the tested NPs at 50 mM dye loading.

Figure S23. Normalized absorption spectra of NPs loaded with 5 mM of R18 salt with different counterions (part 1).

Figure S24. Normalized absorption spectra of NPs loaded with 5 mM of R18 salt with different counterions (part 2).

Figure S25. Normalized absorption spectra of NPs loaded with 5 mM of R18 salt with different counterions (part 3).

Figure S26. Normalized absorption spectra of NPs loaded with 50 mM of R18 salt with different counterions (part 1).

Figure S27. Normalized absorption spectra of NPs loaded with 50 mM of R18 salt with different counterions (part 2).

Figure S28. Normalized absorption spectra of NPs loaded with 50 mM of R18 salt with different counterions (part 3).

Figure S29. Raw absorption spectra of the tested NPs at 50 mM loading. The spectra were not corrected for light-scattering.

Figure S30. Wide-field fluorescence images of 50 mM-loaded NPs with R18/B(CF₃)₄ (a), R18/F5-3PB-OH (b), R18/B₂₁H₁₈ (c), R18/F5-TPB (d), R18/F6-TPB (e), R18/F12-TPB (f). Excitation was done by 532 nm laser with a power density of 0.08 W/cm². Image size is 27×27 μm.

Figure S31. Confocal images of KB cells, incubated for 3h with dye-loaded PLGA NPs. NPs were loaded at a concentration of 50 mM with R18/C10₄ (a), R18/BF₄ (b), R18/PF₆ (c), R18/B(CF₃)₄ (d), R18/F5-3PB-OH (e), R18/B₂₁H₁₈ (f), R18/F5-TPB (g), R18/F6-TPB (h), R18/F12-TPB (i). Excitation was done with a 561 nm laser, emission collected from 570 to 650 nm. For images (a-f) the intensity of the NP channel was divided by two for better visibility. Membranes were stained with wheat-germ agglutinin-Alexa488 (in green).

Figure S32. Confocal images of KB cells, incubated for 3h with 50 mM R18/B(CF₃)₄-loaded PLGA NPs before (a) and after dialysis with 1 mM cyclodextrin (b). Excitation of NPs was done with 561 nm laser, emission collected from 570 to 650 nm (red hot). Membranes were stained with wheat-germ agglutinin-Alexa488 (green).

Figure S33. Confocal images of KB cells, incubated for 3h with 50 mM R18/F5-TPB-loaded PLGA NPs before (a) and after dialysis with 1 mM cyclodextrin (b). Excitation of NPs was done with 561 nm laser, emission collected from 570 to 650 nm (red hot). Membranes were stained with wheat-germ agglutinin-Alexa488 (green).

3. Supplementary tables

Table S1. Conditions for ion exchange to obtain R18-counterion pairs and the reaction yield.

Product	Starting counterion salt	Equivalents of counterion salt	Eluent (DCM/MeOH)	Product yield, %
R18/BF ₄	NaBF ₄	10	90/10	54
R18/PF ₆	KPF ₆	10	90/10	71
R18/B(CN) ₄	KB(CN) ₄	3	90/10	68
R18/B(CF ₃) ₄	KB(CF ₃) ₄	3	90/10	78
R18/F5-3PB-OH	N(Me) ₄ /F5-3PB-OH	3	90/10	73
R18/B ₂₁ H ₁₈	KB ₂₁ H ₁₈	3	95/5	91
R18/F5-TPB	Li/F5-TPB	3	95/5	95
R18/F6-TPB	K/F6-TPB	3	95/5	93
R18/F12-TPB	Na/F12-TPB	3	95/5	96

Table S2. R_f values of the tested R18 ion pairs based on thin layer chromatography in dichloromethane.

Ion pair	R _f
R18/ClO ₄	0
R18/BF ₄	0
R18/PF ₆	0.01
R18/B(CN) ₄	0.01
R18/B(CF ₃) ₄	0.27
R18/F5-3PB-OH	0.01
R18/B ₂₁ H ₁₈	0.45
R18/F5-TPB	0.47
R18/F6-TPB	0.57
R18/F12-TPB	0.66

Table S3. LogP_{HWA} of the tested R18 ion pairs and corresponding standard deviation (SD).

Ion pair	LogP _{HWA}	SD
R18/ClO ₄	-2.74	0.03
R18/BF ₄	-2.69	0.02
R18/PF ₆	-2.66	0.03
R18/B(CN) ₄	-2.20	0.07
R18/B(CF ₃) ₄	-1.51	0.09
R18/F5-3PB-OH	-0.90	0.02
R18/B21H18	-0.36	0.03
R18/F5-TPB	0.74	0.03
R18/F6-TPB	1.18	0.06
R18/F12-TPB	1.21	0.05

Table S4. Properties of 5 mM loaded NPs of R18 with different counterions.

Counterion used in NP preparation	Quantum yield before dialysis	SD ^a	Size (nm) ^b
ClO ₄	0.81	0.01	48
BF ₄	0.66	0.06	42
PF ₆	0.70	0.05	43
B(CN) ₄	0.76	0.01	44
B(CF ₃) ₄	0.51	0.01	42
F5-3PB-OH	0.43	0.01	45
B ₂₁ H ₁₈	0.78	0.01	43
F5-TPB	0.94	0.03	47
F6-TPB	0.91	0.02	44
F12-TPB	0.87	0.01	42

^aStandard deviation of the mean (n = 3). ^bStandard deviation of DLS measurement was systematically ± 2 nm.

Table S5. Properties of NPs loaded at 50 mM of R18 with different counterions.^a

Counterion used in NP preparation	ClO ₄	BF ₄	PF ₆	B(CN) ₄	B(CF ₃) ₄	F5-3PB-OH	B21H18	F5-TPB	F6-TPB	F12-TPB
Quantum yield before dialysis	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.16	0.1	0.49	0.55	0.49	0.48
SD	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.02
Quantum yield after dialysis	0.21	0.18	0.21	0.23	0.31	0.14	0.46	0.55	0.49	0.49
SD	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.01	0.08	0.02	0.01	0.04
Fluorescence anisotropy before dialysis	0.025	0.026	0.026	0.024	0.023	0.019	0.010	0.001	0.002	0.001
SD	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.007	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
Fluorescence anisotropy after dialysis	0.033	0.039	0.036	0.040	0.072	0.047	0.007	0.001	0.001	0.001
SD	0.000	0.002	0.002	0.000	0.018	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Size (nm)	288	366	241	163	50	59	47	47	47	46
SD (nm)	24	107	29	9	2	2	1	4	2	4
PDI	0.14	0.2	0.12	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.08
SD	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.03
Dye encapsulation	0.51	0.58	0.57	0.51	0.59	0.9	0.83	0.92	0.95	0.99
SD	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.01

^aStandard deviation of the mean (n = 3).

Table S6. Spectral properties of 50 mM loaded NPs of R18 with different counterions.

Counterion used in NP preparation	Absorption maximum (nm)	Fluorescence maximum (nm)
ClO ₄	568	587
BF ₄	568	587
PF ₆	565	587
B(CN) ₄	564	587
B(CF ₃) ₄	559	587
F5-3PB-OH	559	587
B ₂₁ H ₁₈	560	587
F5-TPB	557	581
F6-TPB	555	580
F12-TPB	555	579
ClO ₄ in MeOH	556	577
ClO ₄ in phosphate buffer	568	589